

PSYCHOLOGICAL VULNERABILITY OF FOREIGN STUDENTS

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Abstract

Psychological and social vulnerability remain one of the most common problems of psychological well-being among young people around the world. The article presents the authors' view on the problem of successful adaptation of foreign students in Russian universities. In the process of integration, foreign students are exposed to psychological vulnerability. The purpose of the study is to analyze the features of the psycho-emotional state associated with adaptation processes among international students. Constructive communication is one of the possible ways to overcome the anxiety and vulnerability of foreign students. A teacher – «facilitator» will not always demand excellence from students in completing assignments, but will also increase self-esteem and self-confidence in those students whose anxiety has become a constant feature. The authors offer a number of recommendations for university teachers and tutors of student groups to eliminate anxiety and psychological vulnerability of foreign students in the classroom and in extracurricular communication, they share their work experience. University teachers and tutors should pay special attention to the topic of self-assessment of foreign students creating an atmosphere of cooperation while teaching.

Keywords: psychological vulnerability, foreign student, higher education, teacher, anxiety.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the present political and economic situation in Russia, the role of international cooperation is significantly increasing, which, in turn, contributes to the realization of Russia's strategic interests. The expansion of the country's competitive potential, the introduction of high technologies, and reforms in the field of science and education are the basis for the transition of the economy to an innovative type. At this stage, the export of educational services becomes one of the most important tools for innovative development of the country in the context of internationalization of education. The official policy of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation directs Russian universities to step up their efforts in promoting educational services on the international market. The implementation of this task involves the creation of a certain educational environment of a higher educational institution, which will

ensure the success of adaptation of foreign students. According to a number of scientists, «the variety of factors influencing the process of adaptation of foreign students and approaches to their interpretation can be explained not only by differences in research goals and methodological positions of the authors, but also by the actual difference in the socio-cultural situation of different regions of Russia» [2].

Foreign students arriving in Russia do not always follow their main goal of receiving a high-quality education. Conditionally, foreign students can be divided into several categories. The first of them is students sent to study by their parents and for whom the main goal is to obtain a diploma. These are usually the children of wealthy parents, often upper middle class, who consider their education as a stage in an already established career ladder. Therefore, representatives of this category do not actually attend classes, do not understand anything and do not seek to understand, knowing about the low probability of expulsion. All the time that, for example, their parents, who were educated in the Soviet Union, were engaged in mastering the curriculum, these students spend on entertainment: traveling, going to cafes, shops, relaxing, etc. Even if they are expelled from one university for failing, another university is highly likely to take them to study on an individual trajectory. The next category of international students are students who really would like to get an education, but cannot do it at a high level, spending a lot of time studying, because they have to work to pay for tuition and accommodation in such an environment. They do not always know Russian well, as they live together with immigrants from their country. Nevertheless, they are rarely expelled from the university because of their poor academic performance. The third category of international students is those who come exclusively to work. As a rule, they have some level of Russian, and studying at a master's, postgraduate or internship program lets them legally stay in the country. Obtaining a work permit in the Russian Federation involves a number of difficulties both for employers and for foreign citizens themselves. The way out of this situation is to get further education. Russian universities that teach foreign students face a difficult choice: expel foreigners for low academic performance, primarily due to poor knowledge of the Russian language and / or English, or reduce requirements for them, which is dictated by the importance of such a criterion when evaluating a university as the proportion of foreign students in the total number of students. Mass expulsions of foreigners can lead to a decrease in the competitiveness of Russian universities, which contradicts the goals set by the administration.

The growing interest to international students in Russian establishments and the creation of a favorable educational environment for them in Russia awakens research interest in studying the peculiarities of students' adaptation to completely new living and learning conditions. The present article is the author's take on the methodology used at the Ulianov State University to understand how foreign students feel about themselves in a new socio-cultural environment and what measures can be taken to improve living and learning conditions, as well as facilitate the adaptation process.

2. DISCUSSION

The process of adaptation makes foreign students acquire the necessary skills standards, and stereotypes, with the help of which they adapt to the circumstances of life in a new multicultural space. In this context, E. N. Reznikov considers it a very important problem to «identify the adaptability-maladaptivity of foreign students in the process of their education in Russian universities» [7]. Successful adaptation of foreign students leads to a successful educational process. However, the process of adaptation of international students, the number of which keeps growing (at the I.N. Ulianov Chuvash State University, their number increased from 1000 students in 2018 to 3000 in 2024), is not without problems. Stating and analyzing this problem is the reason for this article to be written.

In a multicultural environment, it can be difficult for foreign students to assimilate the culture of the host country: a foreign student who grew up in a different cultural situation seems to be divided between two worlds, which are inherently different and sometimes conflicting, because in the country of study and in the student's country, for example, ideas about kinship, illness, misfortune, religious beliefs differ. To study in Russia, a foreign student must patiently build relationships between the world associated with their native culture and the world outside of it, that is, the reality of the host country. The psychological state of foreign students is an important factor in their successful integration into the cultural and linguistic structure of the host country. Thus, when working with foreign students, it is important to work in such a way that psychological vulnerability could be eliminated [9]. Vulnerability affects the educational process: if a foreign student is exposed to psychological vulnerability, even a minimal internal or external change leads to serious, often tragic dysfunction, such as suffering, hardship, slowing down or even not developing the student's potential.

Each student learns under the influence of many expectations of his family and society. The problem with international students (mostly students from Islamic countries in Asia and Africa, as well as India) is that they may be reluctant to speak out or express their opinions during classes. In turn, the problem of teachers is that they have to encourage students to express themselves, encourage them to express their opinions in class by asking the right questions and thereby contribute to the mastering of a curriculum.

The authors of this article have been working with international students since 2015 and in their work observe that they strive to conform to the values of the host country (Russia), while not distancing themselves from their families, while remaining true to the family goals and culture of their country. It is impossible to conduct an educational process without taking the time to establish connections with students. We have repeatedly asked ourselves the question: « What factors influence the academic performance of foreign students? ». L. V. Lanina attributed to the main difficulties that foreign students face addiction to food, lifestyle, time difference, the presence of a language barrier, a narrowed social circle [6]. Our study and the analysis of the literature on this issue identified the following difficulties: insufficient knowledge of English, ignorance of the Russian language and difficulties in mastering it; difficulties in adapting to the student's group and teaching staff; difficulties in adapting to living conditions in social life and to the Russian reality in general as a whole [5, 8]. Starting to work with the 1st year students, we observe a kind of duality of behavior the student talks to the group mates, but not to the teacher, remains «mute» as soon as he has to go beyond his usual environment. In most cases, when a student adapts to a new environment, this shortcoming disappears. But a student who cannot speak in class is not deprived of his status as a human being; he speaks through his muteness, speaks with his body, gestures, facial expressions, and even silence. Silence provokes such a sharp reaction from teachers that they struggle to overcome it in order to try to understand its meaning. «Mute» student is perceived as resisting, hostile, or even inferior, but the teacher (and university teachers are mostly women) should realize a simple and understandable idea: this student is someone's son, he also has a mother, and silence is explained by poor knowledge of English or Russian. This is one of the main problems of foreign students, so it won't be easy for him to move from one culture to another. In order to establish relations with such a «mute» student, the teacher should identify positive aspects for himself: for example, even if he does not say anything in the first classes, he looks at his comrades, tries to do the same as they do; he does not express refusal, although he is still very reserved verbally; he looks defensive as if he needed to prepare for a possible imaginary danger. Silence creates a kind of shelter, a way to express distance with this world that does not understand him. In this situation, the teacher acts as a facilitator between two worlds: he allows students to enter the learning world without losing anything from their home world.

Broad inclusion of foreign students in university life is important. Day-to-day communication, implementation of educational influence on students falls on the shoulders of mentors, who are university teachers, including teachers who directly conduct classes for vulnerable students. The mentor, in accordance to the decisions of the chair, instructional documents of the university administration and the faculty, explains the features and procedure of studying at the university, introduces foreign students to the traditions of the city, the university, the country as a whole. It is not so easy to conduct educational work with today's foreign students. The teacher should focus on the whole complex of problems related to the education of students. Education of foreign students is largely related to the peculiarities of their behaviour. A survey of international students, conducted by us in the 1st year of the Faculty of Medicine, showed that they greatly appreciate and welcome their inclusion in university life, so it is necessary to organize sport, cultural and social events. Over the years of educational work among foreign students, the Ulianov Chuvash State University has created a special student council for working with foreign students, which includes representatives of the 1st to 6th years foreign students. To achieve this goal, various events are widely used: excursions to museums, theaters, libraries, trips to Russian cities, holidays, Olympiads in the Russian language, the history of Russia, the work of the cinema lecture hall "Classics of Russian Cinema", "Russian Cinema: history and modernity", our international students took part in the World Youth Festival in March 1-7, 2024 in Sochi, etc. International students are happy to take part in various events, be it Christmas, New Year Day, the Novruz, Tatiana's Day or the feast of broad Carnival. The development of a university-wide strategy for educational work with foreign students can contribute to the improvement of the educational process. In order to socialize foreign students, every September a conversation is held with them at the faculties on the problems of adaptation of first-year students in university society. The mentors familiarize foreign students with the University's Charter, the Code of Ethics of the Ulianov State University, the internal educational regulations and rules. International students took an active part in such events as «Dedication to students», athletics race for prizes of the newspaper «Sovetskaya Chuvashia» and the All-Russian Cross of Nations; creative competition

«Become a star»; All-Russian Ski Track; Student Spring; Science Week; festive events dedicated to the celebration of Defender of the Fatherland Day and the 9 of May Victory Day etc. Excursions to museums and art galleries of Cheboksary, visits to the National Library and museums of the University have become traditional.

The result of the socialization of foreign students in a new cultural environment is the possession of background information about a new cultural environment, understanding of the language, adequate behavior in situations of communication and interaction with representatives of a new culture.

To understand the influence of psychological factors on the teacher's role in teaching, it is useful to refer to the model of A. Underhill [10], which describes the techniques and methods of teaching English and distinguishes three types of teachers. First, the teacher is a «reader» who knows his subject, but who after a while comes to the conclusion that his knowledge is not enough, and then he strives to search for new knowledge that will make him a new level teacher. The second type of teacher is called a «professor» who, in addition to his subject, knows the methods and techniques of teaching, but he still faces problems that he cannot solve, which makes him look for new knowledge and, thus, he becomes a «facilitator» - a teacher who not only knows his subject and teaching methods but also knows how to eliminate the psychological vulnerability of students in his class through communication and create a positive psychological climate for high-quality learning. Although for teachers (regardless of the discipline taught), the development of communicative competence is indeed one of the goals, and, therefore, its achievement is part of the curriculum and is expressed in communication activities in the classroom, very often foreign students fail to achieve this. The lack of successful communication for foreign students is explained by the fact that they need much more time to achieve this goal than, for example, students who study in the context of a familiar reality, without leaving their country [3]. Successful communication in the classroom is based on readiness for communication, almost all components of which are directly related to the psychological level: the desire to communicate with a specific person, self-confidence, interpersonal motivation, group motivation, confidence in their ability to communicate. Consequently, the main factors influencing the success of communication are the knowledge of the target language (Russian or English, while since 2015 we have observed that our international students studying totally in English are better able to speak Russian than English), inter-group relations, inter-group climate, and the personality of the teacher and student [4]. To understand the basis of problems in «student – teacher» communication during oral communication-oriented classes, it is necessary to take into account the public nature of such classes, which simultaneously contributes to psychological vulnerability in relation to the student's personality, as student can hardly express himself in the target language, at least for the first time at the initial stages of training. Thus, if we want our students to have such a willingness to communicate that could help them develop communication competence, it is important to take into account psychological factors, which in class practice boils down to reducing the impact of negative factors and stimulating positive ones. So, over the years of working with foreign students, we have found that they prefer visual learning tools: it is easier for them to view instructions written on the blackboard or study examples in a presentation than to listen to the explanation by ear. Consequently, handouts and technical training tools with visualizations of the material being studied are widely used in classes with foreign students, and the teacher accompanies oral explanations with a large number of examples. Making tasks that involve performing activities and speaking out standing in front of the group using an unstable language tool (poor command of English or Russian, unclear pronunciation, grammar errors) implies a high level of vulnerability. In this case, the student's anxiety will increase, and integration into the context of the host country will not be successful. On the contrary, performing other tasks during classroom work (for example, reading material in one language and translating, even if using the simplest grammatical translation method, into another language) reduces the level of psychological stress in the group as a whole, since all students must invest in completing the required tasks.

On the other hand, when using communication-oriented methods, the possibilities of interaction associated with the risk of anxiety are significantly increased, and students may encounter a situation where they try to convey their ideas to the teacher using their still immature language resources, as a result of which the teacher may simply not understand their students, and their self-esteem in this case can be seriously undermined. To avoid this, the teacher can use the method of internal dialogue while simply imagining himself in the place of a psychologically vulnerable student and asking himself the following questions: «Is it very difficult? I can't do it right? The teacher and classmates will laugh at me. » Awareness of such internal dialogues affects the attitude of the teacher to the student (helps to relieve irritation, fatigue from constant repetition of the same thing) and, consequently, the results of educational activities. The teacher can, in this

case, first, help the student become aware of the fact that anxieties exist, and secondly, stop these negative and limiting thoughts that cause anxiety and replace them by more useful ones. For example, instead of thinking, «this is very difficult», you can let the student know that «this is a problem to be solved»; the teacher can replace the student's thought «I can't learn this» by «I can learn this if I work». When we think about anxiety in the classroom, we mean anxiety that overwhelms the student and contributes to his psychological vulnerability, and this should be eliminated by simply giving students the opportunity to express their concerns on a communicative level. Voicing concerns allows vulnerable students to make sure that their classmates share their feelings of insecurity, that they are not the only ones experiencing them, and then overwhelming anxiety is transformed into motivating one with a positive effect. To identify the most troubling moments, we every school year use a simple, anonymous survey, designed to study what aspects of classes cause anxiety. The study of students' attitudes is more accessible in the teaching process than the study of students' abilities, because it is easier for the teacher to influence attitudes rather than abilities and, therefore, it is possible to improve the learning process. Our survey showed that the most disturbing moments affecting learning are language learning (Russian is characterized by them as complex, beautiful, therefore, the teacher's efforts should be directed to overcome the complexity of learning through the beauty of the language), the learning process (you need to learn according to the laws and rules of the host country, and in order to learn them, teachers conduct extracurricular events (for example, meetings with students of other faculties), communication with native speakers (they can be interesting but sometimes unpleasant). Identifying and voicing such concerns allows foreign students to gain self-confidence (for example, our most vulnerable students tell us that they are still not able to learn well, but at least they can understand the teacher and speak the language correctly).

We try to create an atmosphere of cooperation, not competition: when students are busy trying to make others fail, there is little room for true participation in learning, so we periodically use teamwork in the classroom, making one group compete with another, and the teacher encourages the team to correct mistakes that they have made. Consequently, the mistakes are no longer perceived as a disturbing factor and become a positive motivating moment, because they allow finding out where the student should continue to work in order to achieve their goal, that is, to know the subject. Joint activity of student inter-teams is of a great interest, as it makes possible interethnic integration, growth of the initiative of young specialists in research creativity [1]. An effective teacher will not always demand perfection in the student's answers, but will encourage them to try their hand at using communication tools.

3. CONCLUSION

In Russian universities, the educational environment has not yet been fully adapted for teaching foreigners. The international students have poor English skills for English language curricula, and they are often not interested in understanding the course taught in a language new to them, so special attention should be paid to foreign students in the learning process. Anxiety is the enemy of learning, and efforts should be done to limit its impact in the classroom as much as possible. The most important factor stimulating students' motivation will be the teacher's behavior and the classroom environment. Any teacher has opportunities to reduce students' psychological vulnerability: eliminate the cause of anxiety when possible, and offer the student help in overcoming it. Anxiety can be reduced, in particular, by using the attitude of the teacher and the atmosphere that the teacher creates in the classroom. Based on the above, it can be concluded that the process of socialization and adaptation of foreign students acquires the necessary skills and standards, with the help of which they adapt to the circumstances of life in a new multicultural space.

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